

HIGHLIGHT OF TIPPING CULTURE IN RESTAURANTS AROUND THE WORLD

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Abstract. *This study aims to analyze the impact of tipping culture on hospitality service. The research focuses on the factors provided by many websites which include general background and economic impact. This topic has been analyzed by collecting scholarly written studies about the observed topic and the research tends to understand its impact on the hospitality field to make a conclusion and recommendation to improve. After data analysis, in most cases, tipping is used by restaurant owners to charge more straightforwardly to the guests, while they can provide lower wages for staff. A country's tipping culture may play a crucial role in its hospitality. For this reason, the study presents some solutions adopted in other countries to avoid inconveniences caused by tipping or providing a sufficient salary for workers. In this way, the country will be able to attract a greater number of tourists and foreign investors soon.*

Keywords: *tipping culture, restaurant, guest experience, satisfaction, influence, reaction, appreciation, salary.*

INTRODUCTION

“Tipping, or gratuity, is a sum of money given by a customer to appreciate the service provided by a worker” (indiatimes.com). It is given as an addition to the basic price of the service. The amount of the tip is based on how satisfied the guests are with the quality of the given service. Some countries do not define tips with a fixed percentage, since tipping may not be expected when a fee is explicitly charged for the service (indiatimes.com).

Tipping custom has a long history, but its origin is still disputed. One source mentions it has no clear origin, but most probably it was primarily practiced in Tudor England from the 15th century (investopedia.com). It came from Europe in the 15th century, but it was getting more popular in the United States in the 19th century (investopedia.com). The practice of tipping has roots in England, where waiters get extra money when they perform well.

Dr. Peters and Birardi both mentioned that a 20% tip is the minimum appropriate for the standard tipped workers and that larger tips (more than 20%) should be a sign of recognition for excellent customer service (cnbc.com).

From the middle of the 17th century, boxes started to be labeled “to insure promptness (TIP)” to award waiters for quick yet good service by guests in London coffee houses and other shops (investopedia.com).

This practice reached America from Europe. In the beginning, it was not well-received by Americans, as they saw it as unrelated to the values of a democratic society. What they say about the culture of appreciation and how their tipping, attitudes reflect wider aspects of society. The tipping aimed to establish social status by the elite.

In the 20th century, an anti-tipping demonstration started due to an undemocratic view which created a servant class. The first state that banned this manual was Washington in 1909, followed by Arkansas, Iowa, South Carolina, Tennessee, and Georgia, but it has been ended in 1926, and since then tipping has flourished (bbc.co.uk).

The US is the most tip-friendly country all over the world, but there are huge international variations. "Tipping can be problematic because it seems to create classes, that of the customers,

and that of the service workers, who have to satisfy the customers and sort of 'beg' for the tips," as Ofer Azar, a professor of behavioral economics, said.

Tipping started to be created to express appreciation for the quality of the food or the service or even the kindness of the waiter. Tipping got another function because the restaurant owners were unable to close the wage gap. Nowadays service charge is inevitable for American diners because tipping has become a tradition in American dining culture and these places are not prepared for service-inclusive pricing (eater.com).

Methodology and data specification

To understand average tipping culture and habits, analysis of the secondary data was applied, as mentioned in the references. This study endeavors to analyze the similarities and differences between different countries' tipping cultures.

In Europe, it is highly recommended to check for service charges. Especially in costly Scandinavian restaurants, since service is usually included, tipping is not necessary.

In Germany, even if the service is included, a small "*trinkgeld*" is appreciated (johnlewisfinance.com). In France, "*service compris*" means the bill already includes the tip, but especially in the eastern part of Asia, the lack of any tipping tradition is a symbol of pride (bbc.com).

North America proposes tipping more and more often. The habit of tipping in North America is dominant, and the 15-20% rate on restaurant meals is quite high. Customers used to leave an extra dollar per drink at the bar (johnlewisfinance.com, westernunion.com).

In Central and South America, the practice is to leave 10 % of the bill. Tipping was not always part of the culture, but mainly Mexican overtourism has generated "*propina*" which is appreciated nowadays. 10 % is the normal rate in restaurants, but if a service charge is already added, rounding up the bill is welcome (johnlewisfinance.com).

By traveling around Asia, gratuity is not a big deal. It can be shown by a present or small tip, regardless of the given service, but sometimes this habit can cause misunderstanding being interpreted as begging. One of the five tenets of Islam is about giving alms to the poor, so especially for this culture tipping is related to a holy action.

A social norm is deeply entrenched in North Africa, the Middle East, and South Asia, that is around the philosophy of tip or charitable alms (*baksheesh*). Generally, in these countries tipping is not common, and if the customer leaves a tip the amount is usually quite low. (johnlewisfinance.com).

In Egypt, taking a closer look at *baksheesh*, both dollars and Egyptian Pounds are welcome, in general USD 1-2 (or E£30-40) is enough (bbc.com).

In the Middle East and North Africa, the recommendation is to tip more often, but with smaller amounts. When dining out, in general service charge is added, but it's worth adding a small, symbolic price for the waiter. However, in the United Arab Emirates such as Dubai or Abu Dhabi, tipping is similar to Northern America (johnlewisfinance.com).

In China, there is a sense of superstition and tradition. Gratuity is not expected, and in the past tipping was not allowed. Regarding one of the tenets of China, all people are equal which means none is a servant to another. While China increases its number of grand hotels and restaurants, particularly in not frequently visited areas, giving tips still is somewhere between being considered ill-mannered and a bribe. Historically it was rude, but times are changing. The country still is not keen on tipping, indeed, but gratuity is becoming acceptable in bigger cities because of the increasing number of international tourist arrivals (bbc.com), however, leaving a

small tip is usually appreciated and considered a sign of exceptional service (johnlewisfinance.com, westernunion.com).

Japan is considered where tipping is embarrassing and awkward, except for weddings, funerals, and special events. Regarding a tip-free service culture, foreigners should be warned about this tip-free culture, because in more common situations, they feel offended if they are tipped. Even if tourists know the country doesn't tip, some people still feel the urge to show their appreciation with money. It's not rare to see tourists leaving money for staff at restaurants, then the staff try to give their money back by chasing them on the streets or some [servers politely refuse the tip \(indiatimes.com, westernunion.com\)](#).

Some guests cannot understand people do their job with pride, and “the food was delicious” (*oishikatta*), or “thank you for preparing the meal” (*gochiso sama*) is getting lose their essentials, which perfectly represents money doesn't always talk (bbc.com). They believe good service is part of the culture.

These countries are followed by Cambodia, Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia, India, and Malaysia where gratuities are spreading, but with modest amounts. In India, a service charge is levied on the bill, so giving a tip is not necessary. Based on a survey in 2015 revealed that India was among the highest tipper countries in Asia, right after Bangladesh and Thailand (indiatimes.com, westernunion.com).

Sub-Saharan African region says, “A little extra can enhance the travel experience”. Tips do matter in Africa because thanks to gratuities workers' salaries go up higher. So, in that case, rounding up is not enough to express satisfaction. Guests should hand the extra money directly to the service providers to make sure they receive it. 8-10% or a few local banknotes can cover the expenses for necessities (johnlewisfinance.com).

Due to the underpayment of the service staff and depending on a daily cycle of gratuities, more and more retailers are adding an optional service charge to counter sales.

In most cases, it is about paying staff a lower wage and passing more cost straightforward to the customer. Based on an example, in the US when rising the cost of water, not only the price of the water is rising but also 20 % of tips are needed to pay, meaning tipping is generally based on a predeterminate percentage of the total cost of goods or services and the cost of a gratuity simply raises when the price of goods or service increases (investopedia.com).

Tipflation is related to the raised rates that people “have to tip” at restaurants and for other goods and services. Before COVID-19, tipping for the servers was common by 15 % to 20 % based on the service. Today, that range can be different when faced with a preset tipping screen at many types of businesses, including for such services that were not tipped previously. These tipping screens, which are preset tipping recommendations, often starting at 20% (investopedia.com), often put extra pressure on people's shoulders to tip a higher amount than before. Because tipping is not going away anytime soon, guests should find their comfort level to decide how much they will tip and for what kind of services. Also, with many prices going up due to inflation, tipping has risen accordingly since it's typically based on a percentage of the total bill.

Some countries take tipping culture seriously such as the US, where adding 20-25% to a bill is a normal action, but tipflation presents challenges for both locals and visitors in the same way. The given and the expected amount has increased and the rise of [digital tipping options](#) deepened the complexity further (bbc.com, forbes.com).

Key findings

Leaving a tip has many functions, such as showing the financial status, appreciating the given service or completing the waiters' wages. Mainly, the coin has two sides: citizens gain from higher GDP per capita and a well-being program of higher standard than in other countries, which means service staff is not dependent on tips in the same way; and the bill includes hospitality and hotel services.

Even if tipping itself isn't a habit, rounding up a restaurant bill is normal in some countries, as a token gesture. These days, almost everywhere in Europe, service is commonly rewarded with either a monetary tip or the loyalty of repeat visits (bbc.com).

The main cause of the tipflation can be explained by the expansion of digital tipping which is a part of the company's self-resetting which intends to raise the company's revenue and digital and physical footprints (entrepreneur.com), during the pandemic especially food delivery staff was rewarded by guests (investopedia.com). Virtual tip jars have been set up to help service staff even if they are out of work (bbc.com).

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

Overall, this research tended to show the seamy side of tipping. With tips, some workers can earn more than the regular minimum wage, and restaurant owners who provide the tipping minimum wage can keep their price and cost down, but servers who rely on tips for income can get an insufficient salary. If restaurant owners pay their staff the regular minimum wage, it is on the cards to increase the prices of their goods and services to balance labor expenses. Tipping itself encourages workers to provide their best service to increase their tips. In many cases, tips are not mandatory, and guests have the option to customize how much they tip, but it can be an embarrassing moment as well to leave tips for goods.

Every country has its own rules for gratuities, they are so diverged, that is why, it's important to consider other cultures when traveling. For this reason, researching local tipping customs is highly recommended to avoid offending: some expect tips, but some feel offended by being tipped.

If the staff is fully compensated by its salary, the gratuities are not needed. The unification of tipping is not possible all around the world due to the diverse standard of living, but raising the salary can be a good way not to focus on extra tips to complete the wage. If there are not enough resources to provide it to them, at least the countries should make sure the customers are aware of tipping before their arrival.

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